

ARTWIN

INDUSTRY & CONSTRUCTION
4.0 SOLUTIONS

Report on ARtwin generic developments

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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1. INTRODUCTION	7
2. ROLES INVENTORY	9
2.1. Infrastructure Provider	9
2.2. Infrastructure Operator	9
2.3. Low-Level Component Provider	9
2.4. Resource-Facing Service Provider	9
2.5. Platform Provider	10
2.6. Customer-Facing Service Provider.....	10
2.7. Application Developer	10
2.8. Business End-User	10
2.9. Summary.....	10
3. ROLES RELATIONSHIP & INTERACTION.....	11
3.1. Use-cases	12
4. ROLES PERMISSIONS.....	14
4.1. Infrastructure Provider	14
4.2. Infrastructure Operator	14
4.3. Low-level component provider	14
4.4. RFS Provider.....	14
4.5. Platform Provider	15
4.6. CFS Provider.....	15
4.7. Application Developer	15
4.8. Business End-User	16
5. PLATFORM-SPECIFIC ROLES.....	17
5.1. Remote Rendering Services Creation Platform	17
5.2. ARCloud Service Creation Platform	17
5.3. ARTwin Service Creation Platform	19
5.4. Telecom Platform	20
5.5. IoT Platform	21
5.6. BIM / PLM Platform	21
6. SPECIFICATIONS AND BLUEPRINTS	22
6.1. Remote Rendering Service Creation Platform	22
6.1.1. <i>Introduction to Remote Rendering.....</i>	<i>22</i>
6.1.2. <i>ISAR SDK.....</i>	<i>23</i>
6.1.1.1 <i>ISAR SDK had the following features at the beginning of the project</i>	<i>23</i>
6.1.1.2 <i>Feature Developed in ARTwin</i>	<i>23</i>

6.1.3.	<i>Network Integration</i>	23
6.2.	ARCloud Service Creation Platform	23
6.2.1.	<i>ARCloud Service Description</i>	23
6.2.2.	<i>Image capture</i>	24
6.2.3.	<i>Commercial Tracking</i>	24
6.2.4.	<i>Image Preprocessing</i>	25
6.2.5.	<i>Semantic 2D segmentation</i>	26
6.2.6.	<i>Sparse Map Relocalization</i>	27
6.2.7.	<i>Dense Map Relocalization</i>	29
6.2.8.	<i>Commercial Relocalization</i>	30
6.2.9.	<i>Non-Vision Based Relocalization</i>	30
6.2.10.	<i>Pose Fusion</i>	31
6.2.11.	<i>Sparse Mapping</i>	33
6.2.12.	<i>Dense Mapping</i>	34
6.2.13.	<i>ARTwin Map</i>	35
6.2.14.	<i>Sparse Map Interface</i>	35
6.2.15.	<i>Sparse Map Update</i>	36
6.2.16.	<i>Dense Map Interface</i>	37
6.2.17.	<i>Point Cloud Segmentation</i>	38
6.2.18.	<i>CAD Model Correction</i>	39
6.2.19.	<i>Synthetic of Agent & Segmentation</i>	40
6.2.20.	<i>2D Semantic Segmentation Learning</i>	41
6.3.	ARTwin Service Creation Platform	42
6.4.	Telecom Platform	42
6.4.1.	<i>5G RAN Platform</i>	43
6.4.2.	<i>5G CORE Platform</i>	46
7.	CONCLUSION	54

Table of Figures

Figure 1 - High level view of the ARTwin platform	7
Figure 2 - Stack of Roles	10
Figure 3 - Roles Interactions	11
Figure 4 - The ARTwin platform with the different roles related to low-level components, resource-facing services, platforms, platform of platforms, and customer-facing service.	12
Figure 5 - Client and Server	22
Figure 6 - ARCloud service architecture.....	23
Figure 7 - Example of a RAN platform's graph	43
Figure 8 - Example of a RAN Platform's Blueprint	44
Figure 9 - Example of a split 5G RAN platform's graph.....	45
Figure 10 - Example of a split 5G RAN platform's blueprint	45
Figure 11 - 5G Core Architecture. Source: https://www.viavisolutions.com/en-us/5g-architecture ..	46

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the platform generic developments of WP3. It starts by listing and describing the roles identified in T3.1 as needed to the development and delivery of ARTwin. Next, it provides details on the interactions between those different roles. This helps clarify the place and scope of each role at different stages of developing and delivering ARTwin.

In a multi-tenant environment, it is important to keep each tenant's environment protected and isolated from others. Not only confidentiality and isolation are important, but also providing each tenant with a view showing a contextual information relevant to its role increases its efficiency and productivity. In the generic developments we also try to identify the permissions and access rights that each role must have to accomplish their job.

Because not all the roles might be present in every single platform, we through the sub-platforms of ARTwin, describing them on a high-level standpoint, and identifying the roles involved in a specific platform among with the partners of the consortium that can have those roles.

Finally, we provide technical details about the functional specification of the different platforms. In addition, the deliverable includes preliminary blueprints in YAML format for services and platforms that are mature enough to be detailed. As the development and maturity of those services and platforms advance through the project, the blueprints may see some modifications, but the concept shown here is the most important and remains unchanged.

1. Introduction

The platform’s development in WP3 follows an iterative approach. The first task of this work package (Task 3.1) starts with *platform generic developments* where we define and develop the main building blocks needed to deliver ARTwin using the current features offered by NGPaaS.

This document reports on this generic development activity and serves the following purposes:

- Provide a description of the roles identified in T3.1 for the contractual view of ARTwin.
- Provide the context and scope of the roles.
- Report on the progress of ARTwin generic developments activity.
- Provides platforms’ preliminary blueprints.

Figure 1 - High level view of the ARTwin platform

Figure 1 - High level view of the ARTwin platform shows a high-level view on the ARTwin platform that has been developed in WP2 and provided in D2.2. The ARTwin platform comprises different platforms: Remote Rendering Service Creation Platform, ARCloud Service Creation Platform, Telecom Platform (RAN + CORE platform), and ARTwin Service Creation Platform.

The *remote rendering platform* enables the rendering of complex content on the cloud for low-resource devices. It is based on the ISAR SDK of Holo-Light who is leading this effort. It interacts directly

with the *ARCloud platform* that contains services about image capture and processing, map storage and relocalization. Development of the ARCloud components and services is led by BCOM and CTU.

The communication between the platforms and services that are distributed between the AR devices, the Edge cloud and a remote cloud is ensured by the *telecom platform* that does not only provide low-latency high-throughput connectivity between the devices in the construction site or factory, but also between those services running on site and their remote counterparts. The *telecom platform* itself can be considered as a composition of two sub-platforms: RAN (Radio Access Network) and CORE platforms. *RAN platform* is provided by Nokia Bell-Labs whereas *CORE platform* is provided by BCOM.

Other platforms essential to the functioning of ARTwin but not developed and deployed with the *ARTwin platform* are called *external platforms*. This is the case of the *IoT platform* that will be provided by Siemens in their factory, and the *BIM/PLM platform*. Internal and external platforms should be operated by ARTwin platforms as one unique system. Interconnecting and operating the platforms is the role of the *ARTwin service creation platform*.

In the different stages of platforms, their components, and the services developed on top of them, different parties may intervene in a specific scope. Responsibilities of those parties in the given scope can be described with *roles*.

The rest of this document is organized as follows:

- **Section 2** describes the *roles* that might be involved in developing, delivering or using ARTwin.
- **Section 3** illustrates the chain of roles and their interactions.
- **Section 4** provides some details about the permissions attributed to each role so they can do their job in compliance with the concept of the least privilege.
- **Section 5** shows what roles are relevant and involved in each platform.
- **Section 6** describes functional aspects of each platform and service and provides their respective specifications and blueprints.
- **Section 7** concludes.

2. Roles Inventory

In this section, a generic description of the different roles that exist during project's lifetime is provided. The next section maps relevant roles to the scope of their specific sub-platform. Some roles may exist in the scope of several sub-platform but with slightly different responsibilities whereas other roles may be specific to only one sub-platform. As each sub-platform is a platform itself, we will be referring to the different sub-platforms of the ARTwin platform as *platforms* for brevity.

2.1. Infrastructure Provider

The heterogeneity of platforms and their components requires a diverse range of hardware to be used as *deployment environments* (also called *execution environments*). An *infrastructure provider* has the role of procuring and making a certain type of infrastructure hardware available for use by ARTwin platform or project. This hardware can be 5G antennas in the telecom platform, GPUs in the remote rendering platform, AR headsets and so on. Some of this hardware may be suitable for several platforms while some other platforms may require a specific and dedicated type of infrastructure.

2.2. Infrastructure Operator

Providing and operating an infrastructure may not be the responsibility of the same actor or party. An *infrastructure operator* is not in charge of providing the hardware but is responsible of operating it. This role handles provisioning, configuring, building, and running infrastructures. For instance, if the infrastructure is an Amazon Web Service (AWS), the infrastructure operator is the infrastructure provider itself Amazon in this case.

As different platforms may run on different infrastructure, several actors can play this role with the same or different scope.

2.3. Low-Level Component Provider

The role of a *Low-Level Component Provider* is to develop, test, and publish operational components that compose a service. A Low-level component is the elementary piece of software that serves a specific function and, together with other low-level components, can form a service that provides an eventually useful and consumable service. An important part of the job of a *low-level component provider* is also to accompany the component with a detailed documentation providing an explanation of its interface, API, and other useful information. This does not only help understanding the component compatibility, but also minimizes the effort needed to utilize the component.

2.4. Resource-Facing Service Provider

A *service provider* is the *editor* who connects low-level components and parameterizes them to build and provide a low-level, a.k.a *Resource-Facing Service* (RFS) in TM Forum's vocabulary¹. A resource-

¹ For more information on resource-facing and customer-facing services: <https://inform.tmforum.org/features-and-analysis/2015/12/unravelling-the-enigma-of-resource-facing-service/>

facing service is one that cannot be consumed directly by an end user but instead sits as close as possible to the infrastructure and is used by platforms. In case of spatial computing and rendering, a service will consist of a pipeline of low-level components connected with each other with SLA and metadata defined for each service. In addition to composing and editing, *resource-facing service providers* are also responsible of deploying and operating services.

2.5. Platform Provider

Once deployed by service providers, RFS can then be utilized by a *platform provider* who connects and configures them to create a fully capable *AR platform* according to a set of requirements. In other words, platforms are a composition of RFS and/or other platforms.

2.6. Customer-Facing Service Provider

Once platforms are designed, developed and published, they become ready to be deployed. The deployed platforms offer capabilities that can be built upon to serve business interests. This kind of services that utilizes platforms' capabilities are known as *Customer-Facing Services (CFS)*; delivering them to their users is the responsibility of *customer-facing service provider* who intervenes in the different stages of the operational lifecycle of a service (CFS): deployment, orchestration, updating and upgrading, error-handling and so on.

2.7. Application Developer

Application developer's role consists in developing front-end applications that can be used by end users to perform a business function. To accomplish this, an application developer can do the job in an isolated development environment and/or they use CFS capabilities to develop their applications and publish them in a sort of marketplace.

2.8. Business End-User

A *business end user* is the final link in the chain of roles: it is attributed to any consumer of an application. It can be a factory technician or a construction engineer.

2.9. Summary

We can imagine the roles distributed among a 5-layers stack as depicted in Figure 2:

Figure 2 - Stack of Roles

Each layer provides objects or services to the layer above it and consumes from the layer below it.

3. Roles Relationship & Interaction

Figure 3 - Roles Interactions

In the stack of roles shown in Figure 2, each role offers tooling and capabilities to the role above and consumes tooling and capabilities to the role situated below it. Figure 3 provides another view on the sequence of interactions that take place between the roles at different stages of platform building and service lifecycle.

At the very first stage, the role of developing low-level components that run directly on – and maybe operate – the infrastructure is attributed to *low-level components provider*. The tested and validated components must be published (e.g. uploaded to the catalog of components) so that they can be used to compose resource-facing services (RFS).

The *resource-facing service provider* oversees choosing the appropriate low-level components, connecting and configuring them to compose, deploy and maintain RFS.

At the center of the system are the platforms that have their own internal components. Platforms are deployed on an infrastructure and benefit from available RFS available to enhance their operations and enrich their capabilities. They expose those capabilities in the form of APIs, interfaces, or connection endpoints to enable customer-facing services operations. The *platform provider* role covers all those tasks taking place in platforms' lifecycle.

The *customer-facing service provider* leverages capabilities exposed by a platform to build a customer-facing service. This latter includes the backend components of an application, its databases and storage that compose the application but cannot be presented in their raw form to an end-user.

It is the responsibility of an *application developer* to wrap the CFS with a user-interface corresponding to the end-user device (e.g. tablet, AR/VR headset...) and make it available to the end-user. One actor can play several roles. For instance, HoloLight can have both the application developer and the CFS provider roles. Finally, the business end-user is the final user of the application.

This process is followed in delivering the ARTwin platform and each of its composing platforms.

3.1. Use-cases

The unified Artwin platform addresses three chosen Artwin use-cases (see Figure 4). Each use-case accesses Artwin platform through a dedicated custom-facing service exposing specific interfaces. Some services are dedicated to specific use-cases such as CAD model service (BIM for construction use-case and PLM for industry 4.0 use-cases), but most services will be common to three use-cases.

Figure 4 - The Artwin platform with the different roles related to low-level components, resource-facing services, platforms, platform of platforms, and customer-facing service.

The *Low-Level component providers* (i.e., BCOM and CTU) use the *AR Cloud service creation platform* (SolAR framework) to publish low-level computer-vision based components. These components are assembled together in a pipeline to create resource-facing services for Images preprocessing (e.g., CycleISP for denoising and Wallis filter for highlighting features in textureless areas), Semantic 2D segmentation (e.g., YOLACT for instance segmentation for filtering of moving objects from other processing), Sparse map relocalization (e.g., image keypoints detector and descriptor, keypoints matching algorithm, relative and absolute pose solvers, triangulation methods), Dense map relocalization (e.g., NetVLAD image descriptor, Neural Rerendering in the Wild for rendering realistic images, FCGF for dense point clouds alignment), Pose Fusion (e.g., Kalman filter for weighting the pose sources according to their reliability), Dense mapping (e.g., Cascade Cost Volume for High-Resolution Multi-View Stereo and Stereo Matching for calculation of dense 3D point cloud). Metadata and SLA are defined for each resource-facing service by *resource-facing service providers* (i.e., BCOM and CTU). *Resource-facing service providers* are also responsible for tests, publication on a repository, deployment, operation and documentation of RFS. The *platform provider* then defines which services are connected, with which configuration, and how they are chained together. To ease the building of platforms and to clearly separate roles, a high-level platform (e.g., *Artwin platform*) can be composed of a set of low-level platforms (*AR Cloud, Remote Rendering, BIM/PLM, Telecom*). The platform provider is also responsible of deploying it on the nodes provided by the infrastructure provider,

whether on the device itself, on the edge (e.g., the All-in-one 5G AR cloud case or on-premise edge solution), or on a remote cloud (e.g., proprietary, AWS, Azure, OVH). *ARtwin platform* exposes high-level APIs which can be used by several client-facing services. Finally, the *service-facing service providers* uses the *ARtwin platform* and selects the API to expose according to application requirements. In the context of the project, we plan to develop three front-end applications addressing the three pilot use cases chosen to demonstrate ARTwin. These three applications will be connected to three customer-facing services:

- *The “AR-enabled Factory worker” CFS*: It will expose a remotely rendered image displayed on the AR device showing contextual information to factory workers on the shop floor. This image will correspond to the rendering of a part of the CAD model (extracted from the PLM) required by the workers to achieve his/her task. The CAD model will be rendered from a viewpoint corresponding to the worker’s position and orientation estimated by the *AR cloud platform* in order to register the CAD model in relation to the real space.
- *The “Better construction with AR” CFS*: It will expose a remotely rendered image to display on the AR device showing to workers on a construction site contextual information (e.g., reference BIM models, automatic detection of defects, materials, and tools). This image will correspond to the rendering of a part of the CAD model (extracted from the BIM) required by the workers to achieve his/her task. The CAD model will be rendered from a viewpoint corresponding to the worker’s position and orientation estimated by the AR cloud platform in order to register the CAD model in relation to the real space.
- *The “Production Line Planning” CFS*: It will expose a segmented 3D map of the factory where each semantic cluster of the 3D map correspond to a dedicated element of the factory. It provides for each element its ID and its position and orientation which will let production line planners correct the CAD model of the factory. In this way, the CAD model of the factory will be maintained up-to-date and the planning simulation will be carried out on a factory model corresponding to the actual state of the shop floors.

4. Roles Permissions

This section presents the permissions that must be attributed to each role, giving them the access rights that they need to perform their job. A permission is an action that can be carried out on a protected object.

4.1. Infrastructure Provider

This role describes the owner of an infrastructure that will be used in platform deployments. The infrastructure provider/owner can be the one operating it or not. An infrastructure provider has no specific permissions besides ownership of the infrastructure.

4.2. Infrastructure Operator

The infrastructure operator installs, configures, maintains and operates the infrastructure. To do their job they need the following permissions:

RDCL Permissions

1. *Publish infrastructure*: declare a list of physical or virtual servers and make them available to deployments.
2. *Update infrastructure*: edit published infrastructure to update parameters like IP address or credentials. This can also be adding or removing servers from the infrastructure resources.
3. *Delete infrastructure*: delete a published infrastructure.
4. *Create inventories*: combine resources from one or several infrastructures to create an execution environment that can be used to deploy platforms.
5. *Update inventories*: edit inventories to include or remove infrastructure resources or modify the logical composition of the resources.
6. *Delete inventories*.

Non-RDCL Permissions

1. Physical or remote access to the infrastructure.
2. Read and Write access to the infrastructure.

4.3. Low-level component provider

- *Create components*: For spatial computing components, create them with the SolAR framework and embed them in SolAR modules.
- *Publish components*: upload low-level components like spatial computing components embedded in SolAR modules to a repository.
- *View components*: read access to components.
- *Update components*: edit published components. This can be either changing some parameters and properties or updating the component to a new version.
- *Unpublish components*: remove a published component from the catalog.

4.4. RFS Provider

- *View components*: read access on low level components and ability to use them in service composition.

- *Create service*: create a service by connecting low-level components together, by configuring them, and by defining component level resource requirements, limits and SLA.
- *Update service*: change metadata, components, their configuration, their connectivity, or other service parameters.
- *Delete service*.
- *Deploy service*: Once the “composition and edition” phase is completed. The service provider would want to deploy their service and make it available to its users.
- *Update service deployment*: Service components may fail or get updated to include more features. If the component can perform live update the service provider can choose to rollout a new version to a running service.
- *Delete service deployment*: if a service is no longer needed, the service provider may proceed to delete the running instance.

4.5. Platform Provider

- *View RFS*: read access on RFS (ideally represented as RFB) and the ability to use them in platform composition.
- *Create platforms*: create platforms by composing RFBs, connecting them, configuring them according to platform requirements, and defining limits and SLA.
- *Update platforms*: change metadata, components, or other service parameters.
- *Delete platforms*.
- *Deploy platforms*: Once the “composition and edition” phase is completed. The platform provider would want to deploy their platforms and make them available to their users.
- *Update platform deployment*: platform components may fail or get updated to include more features. If the component can perform live update the platform provider can choose to rollout a new version to a running platform.
- *Delete platform deployment*: if a platform is no longer needed, the platform provider may proceed to delete the running instance.

4.6. CFS Provider

In their own development environment, application developers write code. But from the ARTwin platform they can perform one of the following actions to incorporate functionalities to their services.

- *View platforms deployments*: read access to connect to platforms and consume the services and API they offer.
- *Create CFS*: Develop and create the CFS software and RFBs.
- *Update CFS*: Edit the CFS using parameters, variables, configuration files or eventually RFBs metadata to customize it to the business needs.
- *Deploy CFS*: using RDCL.
- *Update CFS deployment*: update the deployed CFS on the fly from within RDCL.
- *Delete CFS deployment*: delete a deployed CFS when it is no longer needed.

4.7. Application Developer

Application developers do not interact with platforms directly. They wrap the CFS in a nice GUI tailored to the business end-user and their device type. The CFS considered as a backend to their application

can be incorporated with the application or can be available via a remote API. Therefore, an application developer needs to:

- *View CFS deployment*: Read access to CFS or their APIs to connect and consume them.
- *Publish applications in marketplace* and make them available to end-users.

4.8. Business End-User

The business end-user role varies with the use-case, it can be the factory worker, the construction site manager, and so on. They have no defined permissions to platforms or services; they only interact with an application available to them on a device like tablet or AR headset. Basically, they read and provide data and interact with CFS through the application.

5. Platform-specific roles

5.1. Remote Rendering Services Creation Platform

The Remote Rendering Service Creation Platform is based on the ISAR SDK of Holo-Light. This SDK enables remote rendering of applications and allows to customize the connection process (signaling). This peer-to-peer connection can be integrated in various infrastructures. Further information on ISAR can be found [here](#). In this project, the signaling and orchestration of ISAR is customized and developed on the base of the *ARTwin Platform*. Other Partners will be able to run applications they created using ISAR in the Remote Rendering Service Creation Platform. Once completed, the customized client will enable a user to choose between the different applications inside the *Remote Rendering Service Creation Platform*.

Another development focus is the further optimization of ISAR. The most important parameter to optimize is the latency added by the ISAR framework. Based on the current state, the final goal is to cut the occurring latency by half to provide a better user experience. And additional area of interest is the impact of network changes to ISAR: reaction of network changes – e.g. worsened bandwidth for a short period of time or package loss - will be analyzed and improved upon.

One major limiting factor is the 1-to-1 mapping of server instances to clients, which means every client device needs its own VM in the ARTwin ecosystem. During the scope of this project, an evaluation will be conducted to analyze the technical possibility to share VMs between more than 1 client device.

New clients will be developed to support a wider range of devices. Currently ISAR is only supported on the HoloLens 2, but during the project clients for Android IOS and the Magic Leap will be developed.

ROLE	PARTNER
REMOTE RENDERING RFS PROVIDER SERVER AND SDK FOR CLIENT	HOLO
REMOTE RENDERING INFRASTRESS PROVIDER HOLOLENS 2, SERVER, WIFI HOTSPOT	

5.2. ARCloud Service Creation Platform

The ARCloud service creation platform is based on the SolAR framework. This framework allows the creation of computer vision pipelines by connecting low-level components (e.g. feature detection, descriptor extractor, feature matching, Perspective-n-Points, triangulation, or bundle adjustment). A

documentation on SolAR low-level component API can be found on the [SolAR framework website](#). All these low-level components will be published SolAR GitHub or on a private repository if not open. A set of low-level components (related to a dedicated service, a third-party library or a partner of the project) must be packaged in a SolAR module (corresponding to the library including the set of components). Documentation can be found on the SolAR website on how to [create a module](#) and [add a component](#) to it. On GitHub, a dedicated GIT repository will be created per module with the corresponding source code, resulting binaries will be hosted on the binaries' session of the repository. The entity responsible of developing, editing and publishing low-level components is assigned the role of a *low-level component provider*.

In addition, during the project, SolAR framework will be extended to allow cloud distribution of these pipelines. Indeed, SolAR framework is based on [XPCF](#) C++ dependency (cross platform component framework) also developed by b<>com, which provides SolAR framework with all mechanisms to load, instantiate and configure at runtime a set of low-level component implementations used by SolAR pipelines. XPCF is currently extended to also offer features to create ARCloud resource-facing services, such as input and output buffering, to deal with asynchronous services, serialization of data transmitted between services (Boost serialization, ProtoBuf, Flat Buffer) and a communication layer based currently on [gRPC](#) (extendable for [REST API](#)). Therefore, XPCF will provide all functions to transform a SolAR computer vision pipeline into an RFS ready to containerize, including the communication layer to exchange data with other services.

The AR Cloud RFS developed with the SolAR framework based on the XPCF dependency will be containerized in [Docker](#) images. To do so, the [Remaken](#) solution developed by b<>com will be used. Remaken is a meta dependencies management tool supporting many packaging systems whether cross platforms (Conan, vcpkg) or dedicated to a specific platform (apt-get, pacman, yum, zipper, pkg, pkgutil, brew, chocolatey). Thanks to a file describing in a very simple way dependencies required by the RFSs (with iterative dependencies search), Remaken can automatically download all necessary dependencies for the targeted platform and install them into the docker image. Also, the configuration, resource requirements, limits and SLA will be described for each RFS. Then, this docker image is hosted on a distant repository (e.g. [JFrog Artifactory](#)) in order to be deployed on demand. The entity responsible of assembling, editing and publishing AR Cloud RFS is assigned the role of *AR Cloud RFS provider*.

The AR Cloud RFS is chained and deployed on the ARTwin platform. The entity responsible of overseeing the blueprint creation by selecting the AR Cloud RFSs, setting and editing their parameters, chaining them and operating the end-to-end AR Cloud platform is assigned the role of *AR Cloud platform provider*.

Finally, a Unity plugin will be developed to access the ARTwin platform through CFS. This plugin will transmit to the customer-facing services using the ARTwin platform the data captured by the sensors of the AR device as well as the poses of the AR devices estimated by the AR runtime (e.g. Hololens SDK, ARKit, or ARCore). The communication between the Unity plugin and the CFS will be based on gRPC. Thus, any AR application developed with the Unity engine will easily be able to benefit from the ARTwin platform just by adding few Unity mono-behaviours which will extend the capabilities of current AR runtimes by offering AR experience at a very large scale.

Thanks to the AR foundation, a Unity framework offering a unified interface to main AR runtimes, the interfacing of the ARTwin platform will be available for the great majority of AR devices.

ROLE	PARTNER
AR CLOUD LOW-LEVEL COMPONENT PROVIDER IMAGE PRE-PROCESSING, 2D SEGMENTATION, DENSE BASED RELOCALIZATION AND MAPPING, CAD/BIM MODEL CORRECTION	CTU
AR CLOUD LOW-LEVEL COMPONENT PROVIDER SPARSE BASED RELOCALIZATION, MAPPING, AND MAP UPDATE, COMMERCIAL TRACKING POSE FUSION	BCM
AR CLOUD RFS PROVIDER IMAGE PRE-PROCESSING, 2D SEGMENTATION, DENSE MAP RELOCALIZATION AND MAPPING, CAD/BIM MODEL CORRECTION	CTU
AR CLOUD RFS PROVIDER SPARSE BASED RELOCALIZATION, MAPPING, AND MAP UPDATE COMMERCIAL TRACKING POSE FUSION	BCM
AR CLOUD PLATFORM PROVIDER	BCM and CTU

5.3. ARTwin Service Creation Platform

The ARTwin service creation platform is the glue that brings together the different platforms of ARTwin. In contrast to platforms composing ARTwin, it is not a self-contained independent platform. This platform is an abstract platform that doesn't not implement a standalone functionality, but it is rather used to pass configurational parameters to the children platforms (e.g remote rendering, ARCloud, etc.) and customize the global ARTwin platform with internetworking settings for a specific deployment or use-case. It enables the creation and deployment of tailored ARTwin platform.

Since it is an abstract platform, the roles at the lower layers of the stack will not be relevant. The roles involved in this platform are the following:

ROLE	PARTNER
ARTWIN PLATFORM PROVIDER	SIE, ART (in the use-cases of AR enabled factory worker and AR construction)
CFS PROVIDER	SIE, ART
APPLICATION DEVELOPER	SIE, ART

5.4. Telecom Platform

The Telecom platform is an end-to-end 5G system composed itself of two platforms: Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network. Each of two platforms consists of cloud-native container-based services deployed on two different flavours of a Kubernetes cluster. In addition, the Kubernetes cluster themselves can be customized to onboard enhanced features that improve real-time communications, particularly for the interest of the RAN.

The services comprising the telecom platform are described in D2.2. BCOM will provide the components and services of the 5G Core network whereas Nokia Bell Labs will provide the components of the 5G RAN platform. Those two platforms are composed of internal microservices and RFS. The role of low-level component provider is not relevant in this context. The (micro)services that compose those platforms are not necessarily developed by the same organization. For instance, the 5G RAN is composed of a centralized unit (CU) aka RRH and a distributed unit (DU) aka BBU. The CU and DU might come from two different vendors. That's where the role of 5G RAN RFS provider is involved. Similarly, the 5G Core RFS provider is the entity that provides the services that compose the 5G Core platform. The entity responsible of building and editing a platform out of those services will be assigned the role of a *platform provider*. This latter applies to 5G RAN, 5G Core, and telecom platform that combines both. The *telecom platform provider* will oversee the blueprint creation, parameters settings and edition and operations of the end-to-end 5G network.

The roles involved in this platform are summarized in the below table:

ROLE	PARTNER
5G RAN RFS PROVIDER	NBL
5G RAN PLATFORM PROVIDER	NBL
5G CORE RFS PROVIDER	BCM
5G CORE PLATFORM PROVIDER	BCM
TELECOM PLATFORM PROVIDER	NBL

5.5. IoT Platform

Siemens offers and operates **Mindsphere** (siemens.mindsphere.io), the leading industrial IoT-as-a-service solution. Mindsphere enables to:

- connect assets and upload data to the cloud,
- collect, monitor, and analyze data in real-time,
- leverage apps to gain insights that improve efficiency and profitability,
- leverage multiple cloud providers like AWS, Alibaba, Azure.

In ARTwin, connectors to Mindsphere are provided in order to retrieve and visualize IOT information in AR. In addition, connectors are provided leveraging the OPC UA protocol to enable direct status information retrieval from the factory's internal IOT system.

Both connectors are operated on the Hololayer backend that is integrated in the ARTwin services architecture developed in WP 4 and acts as a gateway between the ARTwin platform and the IOT systems that remain outside the ARTwin platform.

ROLE	PARTNER
IOT PLATFORM INTERFACE PROVIDER CONNECTORS TO MINDSPHERE AND OPC UA GATEWAY SERVICES ON HOLOLAYER BACKEND	SIE

5.6. BIM / PLM Platform

Siemens **Tecnomatix** is a comprehensive portfolio of digital manufacturing solutions that helps digitalizing manufacturing and the process of transforming innovative ideas and raw materials into real products. Tecnomatix enables synchronization between product engineering, manufacturing engineering, production, and service operations. The subsystem Tecnomatix Process Simulate allows to Conduct assembly simulation for virtual process verification. It includes a 3D model of the assembly lines and cells and offers a Virtual Reality interface.

Likewise, Siemens **COMOS** is an integrated plant management supporting the entire lifecycle – from engineering to operation. The subsystem COMOS Isometrics is a solution for interactive isometry generation from construction to as-built status. It is based on the central database for COMOS and is used for planning projects such as new plant planning, reconstruction engineering, inventories or inspections.

In ARTwin, data about the target factories and plants originating from the PLM platforms Technomatix and COMOS will be made available in an offline manner and will be accessible via the Hololayer platform.

ROLE	PARTNER
PLM DATA PROVIDER INTERFACE TO ACCESS OFFLINE DATA EXPORTED FROM TECHNOMATIX AND COMOS	SIE

6. Specifications and Blueprints

In this section blueprints are provided in YAML format. Blueprints contain some fields necessary to the functioning and deployment of the platform or service, as well as the different components composing it. The following description of those fields apply to all blueprints:

The *functional_blocks* element contains the list of all the RFBs you can see in the graph, i.e. The RFBs composing the service or platform being edited. Each RFB in this list contains also a list of its child RFBs. The *services* field contains a list of endpoints (IP, port, protocol) exposed by the RFB. It could be empty if the RFB doesn't expose anything. The *priority* field controls the precedence order of deployment. This is useful when some RFBs depend on others or require that other RFBs are running before they can start their work. The *ree* (Rfb Exedution Environment) and *host* describe the execution environment and a specific host within this environment respectively. The *metadata* field of each RFB is the most important field that controls the behaviour of the RFB when deployed. It's a dictionary that contains a list of key/value pair that act as variables. The values of these variables can be used to configure and modify the behaviour of an RFB (and therefore a function or a service) according to the business needs. The key/value pairs or variables passed depend on the specifics of the RFB. This approach presents flexibility over having a predefined set of variables to set. To clarify this last point, consider the same function from two different vendors. The two implementations might not accept the same number and type of input and might not provide the same number and type of output. This means that the RFBs that correspond to the two implementations does not have the same set of variables.

For brevity and readability reasons, some fields may be omitted from the blueprints.

6.1. Remote Rendering Service Creation Platform

6.1.1. Introduction to Remote Rendering

One major pain point with AR devices is the computing limitation. To bypass this factor, remote rendering allows the rendering of complex content on mobile devices through a remote rendering service. Instead of loading and rendering data on the AR device, the application will be rendered and computed on the server and only a video stream is sent back to the device. The communication, however, also works in the opposite direction. In this case, the sensor input will be streamed to the server.

Figure 5 - Client and Server

The client application is always the same. The whole logic is in the server application. The server app is informed which platform the client device is running on, so the server can show the right User Interface.

6.1.2. ISAR SDK

6.1.1.1 ISAR SDK had the following features at the beginning of the project

- Plugin for Unity using XR-SDK
- The Position and Rotation of the user is used to render the image on the server
- The Image is displayed on the client side
- HoloLens2 client
- Post reprojection to stabilize objects in respect to the real world besides the added latency through remote rendering

6.1.1.2 Feature Developed in ARTwin

- Full Audio Support
- Clients for several other AR Devices
- Optimization of the added Latency
- Support for Unity XRSDK

6.1.3. Network Integration

- Orchestration of ISAR VMs
- Development of Signaling for the ARTwin platform

6.2. ARCloud Service Creation Platform

6.2.1. ARCloud Service Description

The WP4 has specified a service architecture describing all the services and the interrelationships between these services (see Figure 6).

Figure 6 - ARCloud service architecture

6.2.2. Image capture

The image capture service runs on the device and oversees relaying the images (RGB, RGB-D) captured by the vision sensors embedded in the augmented reality devices to other services that will exploit them.

Input: None.

Output: Timestamped images.

Parameters: Specification of the sensors for streaming

Blueprint RFBs:

```
metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "image_capture_service"
  services: []
  family: "RFB"
  type: "client_processing"
  metadata:
    input:
      device_config_file: "./config.txt"
    output:
      uid:
        - image_preprocessing_service
        - 3d_sparse_mapping_service
        - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
      image_id:
        - image_preprocessing_service
        - 3d_sparse_mapping_service
        - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
      image:
        - image_preprocessing_service
        - 3d_sparse_mapping_service
        - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
      camera_parameters:
        - 3d_sparse_mapping_service
        - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
  priority: 999
  globalPriority: 999
```

6.2.3. Commercial Tracking

Most AR runtimes provide a tracking solution that can be very efficient when they exploit specific hardware acceleration (e.g. HoloLens). Commercial Tracking services consist of providing to other services the camera pose estimated by AR runtimes.

Input: Timestamped images (internal to AR runtime for commercial solution).

Output: Timestamped camera pose.

Parameters: Service implementation dependent.

Blueprint RFBs:

```
metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "commercial_tracking_service"
  services: []
  family: "RFB"
  type: "client_processing"
  metadata:
    input:
      image_id: "image_capture"
      image: "image_capture"
      camera_parameters: "image_capture"
    output:
      uid:
        - pose_fusion_service
        - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
      image_id:
        - pose_fusion_service
        - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
      pose:
        - pose_fusion_service
        - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
  priority: 999
  globalPriority: 999
```

6.2.4. Image Preprocessing

This service consists of applying a filter to an image to improve the processing of the following services. For instance, denoising, a unification of the exposure time and an adaptive median filter can be applied to enhance keypoint detection in captured images.

Input: Timestamped image.

Output: Timestamped image.

Parameters: Denoising method, denoising threshold, window size of adaptive median filter.

Blueprint RFBs:

```
metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "image_preprocessing_service"
  services:
    - name: "image_preprocessing_receiver"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
```

```

    default: true
    port: []
family: "RFB"
type: "image_preprocessing"
metadata:
  input:
    uid: image_capture_service
    image_id: image_capture_service
    image: image_capture_service
  output:
    uid:
      - 3d_sparse_mapping_service
      - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
    image_id:
      - 3d_sparse_mapping_service
      - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
    image:
      - 3d_sparse_mapping_service
      - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
    camera_parameters:
      - 3d_sparse_mapping_service
      - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
  configuration:
    overall_method: "NN"
    denoising_method: []
    denoising_parameters: []
    color_correction: []
    color_correction_parameters: []
    texture_correction: []
    texture_correction_parameters: []
  priority: 999
  globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.5. *Semantic 2D segmentation*

This service consists of segmenting an image in a region where pixels correspond to the same semantic (e.g., car, building, road, vegetation, or pedestrian). This segmentation is applied to 2D images but can be transposed to the 3D mapping during the triangulation and can be used for various optimization, masking of moving objects, and CAD model correction.

Input: Timestamped image.

Output: Timestamped image (where each pixel corresponds to a class of object).

Parameters: Labeling sensitivity.

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:

```

```

- name: "semantic_2D_segmentation_service"
  services:
    - name: "semantic_2D_segmentation_receiver"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: []
    - name: "semantic_2D_segmentation_update"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "private"
      default: true
      port: []
  family: "RFB"
  type: "image_preprocessing"
  metadata:
    input:
      uid:
        - image_capture
        - image_preprocessing_service
      image_id:
        - image_capture
        - image_preprocessing_service
      image:
        - image_capture
        - image_preprocessing_service
      segmentation_model_update: 2d_semantic_segmentation_learning_service
    output:
      uid:
        - 3d_sparse_mapping_service
        - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
        - dense_pointcloud_segmentation_service
      image_id:
        - 3d_sparse_mapping_service
        - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
        - dense_pointcloud_segmentation_service
      segmented_image:
        - 3d_sparse_mapping_service
        - 3d_dense_relocalization_service
        - dense_pointcloud_segmentation_service
  configuration:
    labeling_sensitivity: 0.8
  priority: 999
  globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.6. Sparse Map Relocalization

This service consists of estimating the pose (position and orientation) of a single camera or a rig of cameras from f (in case of an AR device equipped with multiple cameras) captured at a specific time,

without knowledge of the pose of this (these) camera(s) at a previous time. The relocalization service also use a sparse 3D map previously built by AR devices, and stored by the “ARTwin map” service.

Input: images and a sparse 3D map of the real environment.

Output: The pose of the camera that captured the image.

Parameters: Kind of descriptor used for feature matching and bag of word, the image ratio used for relocalization, parameters for matching features, and parameters of the perspective-n-points algorithm.

Blueprint RFBs:

```
metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "sparse_map_relocalization_service"
  services:
    - name: "sparse_map_relocalization_receiver"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: []
    - name: "sparse_map_relocalization_update"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: []
  family: "RFB"
  type: " relocalization "
  metadata:
    input:
      device_uid: image_preprocessing_service
      image_timestamp: image_preprocessing_service
      image: image_preprocessing_service
      coarse_pose: pose_fusion_service
      map: sparse_map_interface_service
    output:
      pose: pose_fusion_service
      device_uid: pose_fusion_service
      timestamp: pose_fusion_service
      confidence: pose_fusion_service
  configuration:
    descriptor: "ORB"
    bag_of_word: "ORB"
    image_ratio: 0.5
    matcher_parameter: []
    pnp_parameters: []
  priority: 999
```

globalPriority: 999

6.2.7. Dense Map Relocalization

This service consists of estimating the pose (position and orientation) of a camera from a single or a set of images (in case of an AR device equipped with multiple cameras) captured at a specific time, without knowledge of the pose of this (these) camera(s) at a previous time. The relocalization service also use a dense 3D map previously built by AR devices, and stored by the “ARtwin map” service.

Input: Images and a dense 3D map of the real environment.

Output: The pose of the camera that captured the image.

Parameters: The distance threshold of inliers, minimal number of inliers.

Blueprint RFBs:

metadata:

version: latest

app: service

functional_blocks:

- name: "dense_map_relocalization_service"

services:

- name: "dense_map_relocalization_reciver"

protocol: "TCP"

scope: "public"

default: true

port: []

family: "RFB"

type: "relocalization"

metadata:

input:

uid:

- image_capture_service

- image_preprocessing_service

- semantic_2D_segmentation_service

image_id:

- image_capture_service

- image_preprocessing_service

- semantic_2D_segmentation_service

image:

- image_capture_service

- image_preprocessing_service

- semantic_2D_segmentation_service

segmented_image: semantic_2D_segmentation_service

pose: commercial_tracking_service

output:

uid: pose_fusion_service

pose: pose_fusion_service

timestamp: pose_fusion_service

confidence: pose_fusion_service

```
configuration:
  3d_residual_threshold: 0.02
  min_inliers: 50
  priority: 999
  globalPriority: 999
```

6.2.8. Commercial Relocalization

Most AR runtimes provide a relocalization solution which provide the pose of the AR device in relation to their own reference coordinate system. The 3D map used for relocalizing the AR device is not always open and can rarely be used for implementing a specific relocalization algorithm.

Input: Timestamped images (internal to AR runtime for commercial solution).

Output: The pose of the AR device.

Parameters: API dependent.

Blueprint RFBs:

```
metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "commercial_relocalization_service"
  services:
  - name: " commercial_relocalization_update"
    protocol: "TCP"
    scope: "public"
    default: true
    port: []
  family: "RFB"
  type: " relocalization "
  metadata:
    output:
      pose: pose_fusion_service
      device_uid: pose_fusion_service
      timestamp: pose_fusion_service
      confidence: pose_fusion_service
  configuration:
    priority: 999
    globalPriority: 999
```

6.2.9. Non-Vision Based Relocalization

Some sensors allow to roughly estimate the 3D position and/or the 3D orientation of an AR device in relation to the real world (e.g. Global Navigation System, magnetometer, ultra-bandwidth or Wi-Fi positioning system, or RFID). This service consists of providing the position or orientation of this kind of non-vision systems to other services.

Input: None.

Output: Timestamped position, orientation or pose of the AR device, as well as the reference

coordinate system in which this information is defined.

Parameters: API dependent.

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
  - name: "non_vision_relocalization_service"
    services:
      - name: " non_vision_relocalization_update"
        protocol: "TCP"
        scope: "public"
        default: true
        port: []
    family: "RFB"
    type: " relocalization "
    metadata:
      output:
        pose: pose_fusion_service
        device_uid: pose_fusion_service
        timestamp: pose_fusion_service
        confidence: pose_fusion_service
    configuration:
      priority: 999
      globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.10. Pose Fusion

This service consists of fusionning the various poses provided by different services (e.g. Commercial Relocalization, Commercial tracking, Sparse Map Relocalization, Dense Map Relocalization, Non-Vision Based Relocalization) in order to best estimate the real pose of the AR device.

Input: Timestamped pose with confidence.

Output: Timestamped pose with confidence.

Parameters: Not yet identified.

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
  - name: "pose_fusion_service"
    services:
      - name: " pose_fusion _reciver"
        protocol: "TCP"
        scope: "public"
        default: true
        port: []

```

```

- name: " pose_fusion_update"
  protocol: "TCP"
  scope: "public"
  default: true
  port: []
family: "RFB"
type: " pose_fusion "
metadata:
  input:
    pose:
      sparse_map_relocalization_service
      dense_map_relocalization_service
      commercial_relocalization_service
      non-vision_relocalization_service
    device_uid:
      sparse_map_relocalization_service
      dense_map_relocalization_service
      commercial_relocalization_service
      non-vision_relocalization_service
    timestamp:
      sparse_map_relocalization_service
      dense_map_relocalization_service
      commercial_relocalization_service
      non-vision_relocalization_service
    confidence:
      sparse_map_relocalization_service
      dense_map_relocalization_service
      commercial_relocalization_service
      non-vision_relocalization_service
  output:
    pose:
      remote_rendering_service
      sparse_mapping_service
      dense_mapping_service
      sparse_map_relocalization_service
      dense_map_relocalization_service
    device_uid:
      remote_rendering_service
      sparse_mapping_service
      dense_mapping_service
      sparse_map_relocalization_service
      dense_map_relocalization_service
    timestamp:
      remote_rendering_service
      sparse_mapping_service
      dense_mapping_service
      sparse_map_relocalization_service

```

```

    dense_map_relocalization_service
confidence:
    remote_rendering_service
    sparse_mapping_service
    dense_mapping_service
    sparse_map_relocalization_service
    dense_map_relocalization_service
priority: 999
globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.11. Sparse Mapping

This service consists of building and extending a sparse 3D map representing the real world. The map is generally composed of a cloud of 3D features such as 3D points (and sometimes 3D edges). Most of the time, representation of key images (keyframes) used to create this map as well as the relation between these key images and the cloud of features (covisibility graph) are also provided to other services.

Input: Timestamped images and their poses

Output: A map consisting of a sparse cloud of features, a representation of keyframes used to build the 3D map, and a structure representing the interrelationship between the cloud of features and the keyframes (covisibility graph)

Parameters: the kind of descriptor used for the mapping, the parameters of the mapping task itself, the map optimization (bundle adjustment), the map pruning, and the loop closure.

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
  - name: "sparse_mapping_service"
    services:
      - name: " sparse_mapping _reciver"
        protocol: "TCP"
        scope: "public"
        default: true
        port: []
      - name: " sparse_mapping _update"
        protocol: "TCP"
        scope: "public"
        default: true
        port: []
    family: "RFB"
    type: " mapping "
metadata:
  input:
    device_uid: semantic_2D_segmentation_service, pose_fusion_service
    image_timestamp: semantic_2D_segmentation_service

```

```

image: semantic_2D_segmentation_service
semantic_image: semantic_2D_segmentation_service
pose: pose_fusion_service
pose_timestamp: pose_fusion_service
pose_confidence: pose_fusion_service
output:
  map: map_update_service
  device_uid: map_update_service
  timestamp: map_update_service
configuration:
  descriptor: "ORB"
  mapping_parameters: []
  ba_parameters: []
  map_pruning_parameters: []
  loop_closure_parameters: []
priority: 999
globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.12. Dense Mapping

This service consists of building and extending a dense 3D map representing the real world. The map is generally composed of a cloud of 3D points with their color.

Input: Timestamped images and their poses

Output: A map consisting of a dense cloud of points, potentially with their color.

Parameters: Number of images used in MVS. Number of iterations for iterative algorithms.

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "dense_mapping_service"
  services:
  - name: "dense_mapping_service_reciver"
    protocol: "TCP"
    scope: "public"
    default: true
    port: []
  family: "RFB"
  type: "mapping"
  metadata:
    input:
      uid:
      - image_capture_service
      - image_preprocessing_service
      - semantic_2D_segmentation_service
      - pose_fusion_service_service
    image_id:

```

```

- image_capture_service
- image_preprocessing_service
- semantic_2D_segmentation_service
- pose_fusion_service
image:
- image_capture_service
- image_preprocessing_service
segmented_image: semantic_2D_segmentation_service
pose: pose_fusion_service
output:
uid: dense_map_interface_service
dense_map_id:
- point_cloud_segmentation_service
- CAD_model_correction_service
dense_map:
- dense_map_interface_service
- point_cloud_segmentation_service
- CAD_model_correction_service
configuration:
num_MVS_images: 3
num_refinement_steps: 5
priority: 999
globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.13. ARTwin Map

The ARTwin Map service is hosting a global representation of the 3D map of the environment. Many AR devices share this 3D global map, update it (correction, suppression, and extension), or extract information to relocalize themselves in the real environment. The Sparse Map interface, the Sparse Map Update, and the Dense Map Update services will be accessing this map service.

Parameters: Scene representation density.

6.2.14. Sparse Map Interface

This service allows to get access to the global sparse 3D map hosted by the ARTwin map service. It mainly consists of extracting relocalization information requested by the Sparse Map Relocalization service based on a given request including parameters such as a coarse localization of the AR device, ambient lighting (sunny day, rainy day, night, etc), supported feature type (e.g. 3D point or 3D edge), supported feature descriptors (e.g. ORB, SIF, or SURF), etc.

Input: Relocalization information request

Output: A local sparse 3D map including the information requested for the relocalization (3D feature cloud, keyframe representation, covisibility graph).

Parameters: Not yet identified

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest

```

```

app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "sparse_map_interface_service"
  services:
    - name: " sparse_map_interface_reciver"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: []
    - name: " sparse_map_interface_update"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: []
  family: "RFB"
  type: " map_interface "
  metadata:
    input:
      device_uid: sparse_map_relocalization_service
      sparse_map_request: sparse_map_relocalization_service
    output:
      map: sparse_map_relocalization_service
      timestamp: sparse_map_relocalization_service
  priority: 999
  globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.15. Sparse Map Update

This service consists of updating the global 3D sparse map hosted by the ARTwin Map service according to local 3D sparse maps build by each AR device based on the sparse map service.

Input: Local 3D sparse map recently built by an AR device.

Output: None

Parameters: parameters for map overlap detection, map fusion, map pruning and map optimization (bundle adjustment).

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "sparse_map_update_service"
  services:
    - name: " sparse_map_update_reciver"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: []

```

```

family: "RFB"
type: "map_update"
metadata:
  input:
    device_uid: sparse_mapping_service
    map: sparse_mapping_service
    timestamp: sparse_mapping_service
configuration:
  map_overlap_detection_parameter: []
  map_fusion_parameters: []
  map_pruning_parameters: []
  ba_parameters: []
priority: 999
globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.16. Dense Map Interface

This service allows to get access to the global dense 3D map hosted by the ARTwin map service. It mainly consists of extracting a dense point cloud with for each point potentially its color, semantic, and normal. If a service requires to extract a part of the global 3D dense map, a specific request will define the region to extract.

Input: request defining the region of the global dense 3D map to extract.

Output: A dense point cloud with for each point potentially its color, semantic, and normal

Parameters: Not yet identified

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "dense_map_interface_service"
  services:
    - name: " dense_map_interface_reciver"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: []
    - name: " dense_map_interface_update"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: []
family: "RFB"
type: " map_interface "
metadata:
  input:
    device_uid: dense_map_relocalization_service

```

```

sparse_map_request: dense_map_relocalization_service
output:
  map:
    - dense_map_relocalization_service
    - cad_model_correction_service
    - point_cloud_segmentation_service
  timestamp:
    - dense_map_relocalization_service
    - cad_model_correction_service
    - point_cloud_segmentation_service
priority: 999
globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.17. Point Cloud Segmentation

The Point Cloud Segmentation service provides a semantic segmentation of the objects represented as a dense point cloud supplied by the Dense mapping service. The semantic 2D segmentation service will initialize the dense point cloud segmentation by assigning labels to the triangulated points. This service will be utilized to correct, update, and create new CAD models of real environment objects.

Input: dense point cloud with labels from 2D semantic segmentation

Output: labeled dense point cloud

Parameters: reliability threshold of the segmentation

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
  - name: "point_cloud_segmentation_service"
    services:
      - name: "point_cloud_segmentation_reciver"
        protocol: "TCP"
        scope: "public"
        default: true
        port: []
    family: "RFB"
    type: "dense_mapping"
  metadata:
    input:
      uid:
        - image_capture_service
        - semantic_2D_segmentation_service
        - pose_fusion_service
      image_id:
        - image_capture
        - semantic_2D_segmentation_service
        - pose_fusion_service
    image: image_capture

```

```

segmented_image: semantic_2D_segmentation_service
dense_map_id: dense_mapping_service
dense_map: dense_mapping_service
pose: pose_fusion_service
output:
  dense_map_id:
    - dense_map_interface_service
    - CAD_model_correction_service
  dense_map_labels:
    - dense_map_interface_service
    - CAD_model_correction_service
configuration:
  reliability_threshold: 0.8
priority: 999
globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.18. CAD Model Correction

This service will match the so far known CAD objects with semantically segmented point clouds supplied by Point Cloud Segmentation service. Highly confidence matches will be utilized to correct the CAD models in a database. An unknown object will be reported to the operator, which will decide further processing, i.e., annotation and saving it into the CAD model database or collecting more detailed scanning.

Input: segmented dense point cloud and database of CAD models

Output: corrected or new CAD model

Parameters: model similarity threshold, loss function

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
  - name: "CAD_model_correction_service"
    services:
      - name: "CAD_model_correction_reciver"
        protocol: "TCP"
        scope: "public"
        default: true
        port: []
    family: "RFB"
    type: "dense_mapping"
  metadata:
    input:
      dense_map_id:
        - dense_mapping_service
        - point_cloud_segmentation_service
      dense_map: dense_mapping_service
      dense_map_labels: point_cloud_segmentation_service

```

```

    CAD_models_database: hololayer_map_service
  output:
    CAD_model_id: hololayer_map_service
    CAD_model: hololayer_map_service
  configuration:
    similarity_threshold: 0.9
    loss_function: "mean_3d_points_distance"
    max_inlier_distance: 0.01
  priority: 999
  globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.19. Synthetic of Agent & Segmentation

Synthetic of Agent provides a sensor data of a virtual device (e.g., HoloLens) moving in ARTwin map or NavVis scans. It consists of rendering realistically looking images, depth maps, and other sensor data, e.g., accelerometer and gyroscope. The Segmentation part of this service assumes known segmentation of dense point cloud and provides 2D images with masks of individual objects. Together, the rendered images will be used to test the Sparse and Dense map relocalization, Dense Mapping service, and 2D Semantic Segmentation Learning service.

Input: ARTwin map or NavVis scans with semantic labels

Output: 2D renders of a virtual camera with semantic masks, other sensors of a virtual device

Parameters: synthetic device specification, agent movement trajectory

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "synthetic_of_agent_service"
  services:
    - name: "synthetic_of_agent_provider"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: []
  family: "RFB"
  type: "dense_mapping"
  metadata:
    input:
      dense_map: dense_map_interface_service
      dense_map_labels: dense_map_interface_service
    output:
      uid:
        - image_preprocessing_service
        - semantic_2D_segmentation_service
        - dense_map_relocalization_service
        - dense_mapping_service
        - point_cloud_segmentation_service

```

```

- semantic_2D_segmentation_learning_service
image_id:
- image_preprocessing_service
- semantic_2D_segmentation_service
- dense_map_relocalization_service
- dense_mapping_service
- point_cloud_segmentation_service
- semantic_2D_segmentation_learning_service
image:
- image_preprocessing_service
- semantic_2D_segmentation_service
- dense_map_relocalization_service
- dense_mapping_service
- point_cloud_segmentation_service
- semantic_2D_segmentation_learning_service
segmented_image:
- image_preprocessing_service
- semantic_2D_segmentation_service
- dense_map_relocalization_service
- dense_mapping_service
- point_cloud_segmentation_service
- semantic_2D_segmentation_learning_service
pose:
- dense_map_relocalization_service
- dense_mapping_service
- point_cloud_segmentation_service
- semantic_2D_segmentation_learning_service
configuration:
  movement: "random"
  movement_parameters: []
  camera_parameters_file: "./agent_cameras_config.txt"
priority: 999
globalPriority: 999

```

6.2.20. 2D Semantic Segmentation Learning

This service retrains a neural network for the semantic segmentation of input images, i.e., this service updates the Semantic 2D segmentation service. Training data will be supplied by Synthetic Agent & Segmentation service and allows recognition of new objects or improve the accuracy of recognition of the current models and CAD models in the database.

Input: realistically looking renders of a virtual camera and 2D images with semantic masks

Output: retrained neural network for semantic 2d segmentation

Parameters: loss function, initial weights of neural network

Blueprint RFBs:

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service

```

functional_blocks:

```
- name: "semantic_2D_segmentation_learning_service"
  services:
    - name: "semantic_2D_segmentation_learning_reciever"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: []
  family: "RFB"
  type: "dense_mapping"
  metadata:
    input:
      image: synthetic_of_agent_provider
      segmented_image: synthetic_of_agent_provider
    output:
      segmentation_model_update: semantic_2D_segmentation_service
  priority: 999
  globalPriority: 999
```

6.3. ARTwin Service Creation Platform

As explained earlier, this platform doesn't have any concrete implemented functionality by itself. It provides a way to edit the ARTwin platform to specific needs so the different platforms composing ARTwin can operate optimally. Accordingly, this platform inherits its specifications from the different platforms. Additionally, it can introduce new specifications that are not specific to one platform, but for the interoperability between platforms.

At the time of writing this document, the platforms are under development and their respective specifications are provided in the sections dedicated to each platform. The integration of all the platforms is an upcoming task and will determine the look and feel of the ARTwin service creation platform.

Figure 1 - High level view of the ARTwin platform shows how the different platforms are interconnected. As the platforms become more mature in the future stages of the project, RFBs and blueprints will be developed accordingly.

6.4. Telecom Platform

The telecom platform plays a crucial role in providing connectivity for user devices and on-premises running platforms. It connects the services of running on premises to each other (e.g. remote rendering services to IoT or BIM services) and to remote services running in the cloud (e.g. remote rendering services to AR cloud services running in a public or remote cloud).

The performance of the telecom platform needs to meet the functional requirements of the other platforms. Particularly, it needs to ensure low latency between some components. This is the case, for example, of the image capturing service running on an AR device, and the relocalization service. 5G systems present an ideal candidate that meets the strict requirements of AR services.

Like previous generations of mobile systems, 5G systems are architected with two levels:

1. Radio Access Network (RAN)
2. Core Network

6.4.1. 5G RAN Platform

With the emergence of NFV and Cloud computing, the radio access network evolved towards CloudRAN, aka cRAN. The concept brought flexibility in orchestrating RAN real time and non-real time functions based on the resources configuration to meet service requirements.

Real time functions include access network scheduling, link adaptation, power control, interference coordination, retransmission, modulation, and coding. To achieve the required performance, the dedicated hardware with high accelerator processing, whilst located near the user. Those functions are usually implemented in the site deployment of the cell on the gNodeB (gNB) hardware. The collection of real time functions deployed in a distributed manner are sometimes called Distributed Unit (DU).

The RAN non-real time functions include intercell handover, cell selection and reselection, user-plane encryption, and multiple connection convergence. These functions require minimal real-time performance, latency requirements to dozens of milliseconds and are suitable for centralized deployment. The collection of non-real time functions deployed in a centralized manner are sometimes called Centralized Unit (CU).

The simplest way to deploy a RAN is to not split the CU and DU. Instead, deploy all functions on the dedicated gNB hardware. In this case, most RAN configurations are done via the equipment's vendor tools. However, some vendors expose a set of the configurable settings via an API. This can be leveraged in orchestration tools like RDCL to send configuration commands to the equipment. In this case, it is enough to create a platform of one functional block (RFB) that contains the desired command or commands. When deployed, the RFB sends the command that will configure the gNB via its API (REST in our example).

Figure 7 - Example of a RAN platform's graph

Figure 8 shows an example of how the blueprint of the RAN platform in ARTwin might look like. The exact set of parameters can be different without changing the concept demonstrated by this example.

The *functional_blocks* element contains the list of all the RFBs you can see in the graph, e.g. Figure 7.

```

1  metadata:
2  |   version: latest
3  |   app: service
4  functional_blocks:
5  -  name: service_fb
6  |   rfb_list:
7  |   | - functional_bloc
8  |   services: []
9  |   family: RFB
10 |   type: functional_block
11 |   metadata: {}
12 |   priority: 999
13 |   globalPriority: 999
14 |   host: csv-n-a
15 |   ree: ran_k8s
16 -  name: functional_bloc
17 |   rfb_list:
18 |   | - deployTestLineName
19 |   services: []
20 |   family: RFB
21 |   type: functional_block
22 |   metadata: {}
23 |   priority: 999
24 |   globalPriority: 999
25 -  name: deployTestLineName
26 |   rfb_list: []
27 |   services: []
28 |   family: RFB
29 |   type: deployTestLineName
30 |   metadata:
31 |   | TLN: TLN-5G
32 |   priority: 999
33 |   globalPriority: 999

```

Figure 8 - Example of a RAN Platform's Blueprint

When deploying a split gNB (CU + DU), the RAN platform has two leaf level RFBs instead of one. The split obviously leads to more configuration options on both sides. Figure 9 shows how the platform's graph would look like, and Figure 10 shows an excerpt of the corresponding blueprint in YAML format.

Figure 9 - Example of a split 5G RAN platform's graph

The RRU and RCC are the 4G acronyms of DU and CU respectively. In this example both were deployed using containers and orchestrated with a Kubernetes cluster. In the RFB's metadata we can see some information regarding this kind of execution environments like the `node_selector` and the selection of network cni plugin. The RRU also has the variable `use_fpga` set to true, which enables it to run on an FPGA instead of the CPU. On the other hand, the RCC needs to know the IP addresses to use for its connections with RRU and the core network.

```
- name: rru_vyfs
  rfb_list: []
  services: []
  family: RFB
  type: rru
  metadata:
    node_selector: airframe1
    rru_image_tag: fpga
    primary_cni: calico
    use_fpga: 'True'
    rru_fpga_id: '0'
  priority: 999
  globalPriority: 999
- name: rcc_aocy
  rfb_list: []
  services: []
  family: RFB
  type: rcc
  metadata:
    epc_ip: 192.168.0.16
    node_selector: airframe1
    secondary_cni: flannel
    rcc_if_name_epc: eth1
    rcc_image_tag: fpga
    s1u_pub_ip: 192.168.60.91
  priority: 999
  globalPriority: 999
```

Figure 10 - Example of a split 5G RAN platform's blueprint

6.4.2. 5G CORE Platform

Figure 11 - 5G Core Architecture. Source: <https://www.viavisolutions.com/en-us/5g-architecture>

As stated in D2.2, not all of functions presented in Figure 11 will be implemented, only the following subset is needed:

AMF

The Access and Mobility Management function (AMF) is the entry point in the Core Control Plane for the UE and the NG-RAN. It provides the termination of RAN Control Plane signaling interface (N2), as well as the termination of UE signaling interface (N1), also named the NAS. The AMF supports registration, connection, reachability and mobility management, access authentication.

This component is split compliant with a microservice architecture and is composed of different types of containers that are managed by a Kubernetes PaaS.

- N1N2MessageTransfer container: N1N2_Message_Transfer microservice is responsible for UE PDU Session management.

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "amf_n1n2messagetransfer"
  services:
    - name: "n1n2"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: 8080
  family: "RFB"
  type: "5g_cn"
  metadata:
    AMQP_DNS: wef-rabbitmq
    transport_port: 8080
    log_level: debug

```

```
queue: amqp://guest:guest@localhost:5672
pistache_nb_thread: 2
smf_pdu_session_url: http://smf-pdusession-server:8080/nsmf-
pdusession/v1
```

- N2Link container

N2_LINK microservice ensures the AMF interface with gNBs and UEs. It is responsible for signaling protocols interworking between SCTP and AMQP for gNB and UE sessions management. As a gateway, it routes the request to the relevant AMF microservice.

```
metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "amf_n2link"
  services:
    - name: "amf_n2link"
      protocol: "SCTP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: 38412
  family: "RFB"
  type: "5g_cn"
  metadata:
    NGAP_DNS: amf-n2link
    AMQP_DNS: wef-rabbitmq
    network_ip: [0.0.0.0]
    transport_port: 38412
    transport_protocol: SCTP
    log_level: debug
    threadpool_nb_worker: 3
    threadpool_queue_size: 1024
    queue: amqp://guest:guest@localhost:5672
```

- NgSetup container

The NG_SETUP microservice is responsible for gNB sessions management. It analyses NGAP Setup Request messages received on its queue, registers the gNB and posts NGAP setup response on the N2_LINK's gNB dedicated queue.

```
metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "amf_ngsetup"
  services: []
  family: "RFB"
```

```

type: "5g_cn"
metadata:
  NGAP_DNS: amf-n2link
  USER: xxx
  PASSWORD: yyy
  RABBIT_SERVER_IP: wef-rabbitmq

```

- RabbitMQ container for message queueing: This is an auxiliary container and we will not be specifying the blueprint here as it is not an integral part of a 5G Core network but rather depends on the implementation.

SMF

The Session Management function (SMF) functionalities include session management (establishment, modification, release), encompassing tunnel maintenance between the UPF and the AN (Access Network), UE IP address allocation, selection and control of UPF, traffic steering configuration, Control and coordination of charging data collection at UPF, and other functions.

This component is split compliant with a microservice architecture and is composed of different types of containers that are managed by a Kubernetes PaaS.

- SMF Event Exposure Server container :

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "smf_eventexposure_server"
  services:
    - name: "smf-event-exposure-server"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: 8080
    - name: "smf-event-exposure-serve"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: 8443
  family: "RFB"
  type: "5g_cn"
  metadata:
    NF_APIROOT: "http://smf-event-exposure-server:8080"
    THORNTAIL_JAEGER_REMOTE_REPORTER_HTTP_ENDPOINT: "http://wef-jaeger-
collector:14268/api/traces"
    NF_NRF_READYCHECK: "http://wef-nrf-controller:80/nnrf-disc/v1/nf-
instances?target-nf-type=NRF&requester-nf-type=NRF"
    NF_NRF_APIROOT: "http://wef-nrf-controller:80"

```

- SMF PDU Session Server container :

This container creates, modifies and deletes SM contexts for PDU Sessions upon receiving N1 message notification from AMF carrying the NAS SM messages.

```
metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "smf_pdusession_server"
  services:
    - name: "smf-pdusession-server"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: 8080
    - name: "smf-pdusession-server"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: 8443
  family: "RFB"
  type: "5g_cn"
  metadata:
    NF_SPGW_APIROOT: "http://spgw-c-frontend:10010/spgw-c-frontend/v2"
    NF_APIROOT: "http://smf-pdusession-server:8080"
    NF_AMF_APIROOT: "http://amf-nln2messagetransfer:8080"
    THORNTAIL_JAEGER_REMOTE_REPORTER_HTTP_ENDPOINT: "http://wef-jaeger-
collector:14268/api/traces"
    NF_NRF_READYCHECK: "http://wef-nrf-controller:80/nnrf-disc/v1/nf-
instances?target-nf-type=NRF&requester-nf-type=NRF"
    NF_NRF_APIROOT: "http://wef-nrf-controller:80"
```

NRF

The Network Repository Function (NRF) provides service discovery function to allow any NF to discover what instances of others NF are available and their related information. It maintains the NF profile of available NF instances and their supported services. NFs that wish to be discovered register their profiles in the NRF. Other NFs send *NF Discovery Request* to the NRF.

The NRF also maintains the health status information of the registered NFs and can notify about newly registered/updated/deregistered NF to the subscribed NF service consumer.

- NRF Discovery container: this container allows a NF to discover services offered by other NF.

```
metadata:
  version: latest
```

```

app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "nnrf-discovery"
  services:
    - name: "nnrf-discovery"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: 80
    - name: "nnrf-discovery"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: 443
  family: "RFB"
  type: "5g_cn"
  metadata:
    NNRF_NFM_DNS: "nnrf-nfmanagement"
    JAEGER_DNS: "wef-jaeger-collector"
    THORNTAIL_JAEGER_REMOTE_REPORTER_HTTP_ENDPOINT: "http://wef-jaeger-
collector:14268/api/traces"
    THORNTAIL_HTTP_KEYSTORE_PATH: "nnrf-disc.jks"
    NF_NRF_APIROOT: http://nginx-ingress-controller:80
    NF_NRF_DISC_VALIDITYPERIOD: "90"

```

- **NRF NF Management container:** This container allows any NF to register, update or deregister its profile in the NRF. It also allows any NF to subscribe to be notified of newly registered NF instances and services.

```

metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "nnrf-nfmanagement"
  services:
    - name: "nnrf-nfmanagement"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: 80
    - name: "nnrf-nfmanagement"
      protocol: "TCP"
      scope: "public"
      default: true
      port: 443
  family: "RFB"
  type: "5g_cn"

```

```
metadata:
  JAEGER_DNS: "wef-jaeger-collector"
  THORNTAIL_JAEGER_REMOTE_REPORTER_HTTP_ENDPOINT: "http://wef-jaeger-
collector:14268/api/traces"
  THORNTAIL_HTTP_KEYSTORE_PATH: "nnrf-nfm.jks"
```

UDM

The Unified Data Management (UDM) handles the generation of authentication credentials used for user identification. It supports access authorization based on subscription data, subscription management, and other functions. Its software is based on the open source project free5GC. It is composed of two different types of containers: one containing the database and another one containing the software handling the logic of the service. These containers are managed by a Kubernetes PaaS.

Below is an example of what the configuration of the main container could look like:

```
metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "nnrf-discovery"
  services:
    - name: "nudm-sdm"
    - name: "nudm-uecm"
    - name: "nudm-ueau"
    - name: "nudm-ee"
    - name: "nudm-pp"
  family: "RFB"
  type: "5g_cn"
  metadata:
    sbi:
      scheme: http
      registerIPv4: 127.0.0.1 # IP used to register to NRF
      bindingIPv4: 127.0.0.1 # IP used to bind the service
      port: 29503
      tls:
        log: free5gc/udmsslkey.log
        pem: free5gc/support/TLS/udm.pem
        key: free5gc/support/TLS/udm.key
    udrclient:
      scheme: http
      ipv4Addr: 127.0.0.1
      port: 29504
    nrfclient:
      scheme: http
      ipv4Addr: 127.0.0.1
      port: 29510
```

```
nrfUri: http://localhost:29510
keys:
  udmProfileAHNPublicKey: 5a8d38864820197c3394b92613b20b91633cbd89711
9273bf8e4a6f4eec0a650
  udmProfileAHNPrivateKey: c53c22208b61860b06c62e5406a7b330c2b577aa55
58981510d128247d38bd1d
  udmProfileBHNPublicKey: 0472DA71976234CE833A6907425867B82E074D44EF9
07DFB4B3E21C1C2256EBCD15A7DED52FCBB097A4ED250E036C7B9C8C7004C4EEDC4F068CD7B
F8D3F900E3B4
  udmProfileBHNPrivateKey: F1AB1074477EBCC7F554EA1C5FC368B1616730155E
0041AC447D6301975FECDA
```

AUSF

The Authentication Server Function (AUSF) has a single function, that is user's authentication. Its software is based on the open source project free5GC. It is composed of one container containing the software handling the logic of the service that is managed by a Kubernetes PaaS.

Below is an example of what the configuration of the main container could look like:

```
metadata:
  version: latest
  app: service
functional_blocks:
- name: "nnrf-discovery"
  services:
    - name: "nausf-auth"
    - name: "nudm-uecm"
    - name: "nudm-ueau"
    - name: "nudm-ee"
    - name: "nudm-pp"
  family: "RFB"
  type: "5g_cn"
  metadata:
    sbi:
      scheme: http
      registerIPv4: 127.0.0.1 # IP used to register to NRF
      bindingIPv4: 127.0.0.1 # IP used to bind the service
      port: 29509
    nrfUri: http://localhost:29510
  plmnSupportList:
    - mcc: 208
      mnc: 93
    - mcc: 123
      mnc: 45
  groupId: ausfGroup001
```

UPF

The User Plane Function (UPF) is connected to the NG-RAN, the control plane, and the external data network via N3, N4, and N6 interfaces respectively.

The main functions of UPF are external PDU session point of interconnect to data network and packet routing & forwarding.

At the time of writing this document, the UPF NF has its software based on OpenvSwitch (OVS) installed in a virtual machine (VM). For the initial prototype the UPF is not part of the container-based deployment orchestrated by Kubernetes. It will be deployed on a hypervisor, such as Openstack or KVM. The switching service for the data path provided by UPF is more complex than other Core Network functions. The evolution of the UPF implementation is going to be studied for the final prototype.

7. Conclusion

The elements of the contractual view of ARTwin are defined by the roles, their scope and permissions. From infrastructure provider through platform provider to application developer and business end-users, different roles take place at different stages of ARTwin lifecycle.

The goal of the undergoing development effort of the platforms and their components is to make ARTwin easily and flexibly deployable, and compatible with a wide variety of AR devices. This document provides a functional description for each component and platform. Preliminary blueprints in the form of YAML files are given for the components that are mature enough to be detailed.

The generic development is an ongoing task as well as platform's specific development from other tasks of WP3.